

A New Synthesis of 3-Bromoflavones

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The formation of 3-haloflavones¹ has been carried out by various workers via 2-halodibenzoylmethanes. The 3-haloflavones rearrange in alkaline condition to give 2-benzoylcoumarones². Griseofulvin does not react with bromine in acetic acid under ordinary conditions but reacts in presence of mercuric acetate to give 5-bromo derivative³. We report here a direct synthesis of 3-bromoflavones from flavones by reacting with bromine in acetic acid in

presence of catalytic amount of mercuric acetate. The identity of 3-bromoflavone (2a) was established on the basis of analytical, spectral and chemical evidences: ν_{\max} (nujol) 1650 (conjugated C=O), 1625, 1560, 1495, 1350 (aromatic) and 840 cm^{-1} (=C—Br); pmr δ (CDCl_3) 2.50 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 3.93 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 6.70—8.00 (7H, m, ArH). On refluxing with alcoholic NaOH for 1 h, 2a gave 3a which was identified on the basis of its chemical reactions and direct comparisons (m.m.p.) with an authentic sample prepared by known method⁴.

The reaction possibly proceeds through the formation of intermediate 3-acetoxymeric derivative of flavone (not isolated), which reacts with bromine in acetic acid giving 3-bromoflavone.

The starting flavones were prepared by known methods⁵.

Experimental

General procedure: To a flavone (0.01 mol) in AcOH (20 ml), mercuric acetate (1.6 g, 0.005 mol) was added and the solution was boiled for 5 min. To this hot solution bromine (0.01 mol) in acetic acid was added with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was kept for 30 min. Woolly crystals got separated. This product was crystallised from acetic acid giving pinkish woolly needles of 2 (70—80%): 2a, m.p. 153°; 2b, 126°; 2c, 151°; all the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and Br analyses.

3-Bromoflavones (2a—c) were subjected to rearrangement which alcoholic NaOH to give the corresponding 2-arylcoumarones (3a—c). Each compound was identified on the basis of m.p. and m.m.p. determinations with samples prepared by literature methods.

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- a; R₁=CH₃, R₂=OCH₃
 b; R₁=R₂=H
 c; R₁=CH₃, R₂=H